

Deliverable D2.1 Landscape analysis of existing ontologies and recommendations on a set of imaging ontologies

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Authors	Dario Longo, François Sherwood, Maria Mírza
Contributors	Aybuke Yoldas, Matthew Hartley
Reviewers	Antje Keppler, Aastha Mathur
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

(EMBL-)EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
API	Application Programming Interface
BFO	Basic Formal Ontology
BIA	BioImage Archive
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
EMBL	European Molecular Biology Laboratory
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FBbi	Biological Imaging Methods Ontology
HP	Human phenotype ontology
IDR	Image Data Resource
JERM	Just Enough Results Model ontology
MP	Mammalian phenotype ontology
OBI	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations
OLS	Ontology Lookup Service
PID	Persistent Identifiers
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REMBI	Recommended Metadata for Biological Images
SSBD	Systems Science of Biological Dynamics Database

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Executive Summary

Image data is one of the fastest growing types of research data. It is characterized by rapid advances in imaging technologies and workflows of increasing complexity, making metadata standardization and maintaining the standards a challenging task. One of the main aims of the foundingGIDE project is to harmonise image metadata across data repositories. To that end, a common set of ontologies is a crucial building block. D2.1 presents a comprehensive analysis of the current landscape of ontologies relevant to biological and preclinical imaging data. Here we identify and evaluate existing ontologies and integrate the findings into recommendations for supporting harmonized image data representation and enable interoperability of global image data resources. The recommendations from D2.1 will also serve as a guidance for data producers to adopt, in order to make their data easier to incorporate in open data repositories.

1. Introduction

Biological and preclinical imaging technologies are evolving rapidly, producing vast and complex datasets across a wide range of research samples and modalities bringing major challenges for data interoperability. Ontologies are pivotal to make imaging data interoperable, machine-readable and aligned with all of the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles. Ontologies are frameworks used to standardize the process of linking data to a broader context. Here, we provide recommendations on a set of ontologies for describing biological image datasets and a set of ontologies for describing preclinical imaging datasets.

Ontologies are useful for efficient data management and for enabling datasets interoperability. They can be used as controlled vocabulary of terms in metadata values or to provide semantics to the structure of metadata in dataset repositories. This use of standardized terms ensures that different researchers refer to the same concepts when describing a dataset and promotes interoperability across datasets and across multiple repositories.

This landscape analysis addresses a foundational need of interoperability and aims to support the global imaging community practices across biological and preclinical imaging modalities. This work is laying the groundwork for an interoperable ecosystem and enables more informed decisions about ontology selection. Ultimately, this work strengthens the ability of the research community to generate interoperable imaging data and contributes to the broader goal of building an open global image data ecosystem.

Here we present the landscape analysis of ontologies structured into biological and preclinical domains. Following this introduction, the second section presents the landscape analysis of ontologies relevant to biological imaging, detailing the identification of relevant ontologies, the domains they cover, and their use. This section also presents an evaluation framework, discusses risks and deal-breakers, and provides an overall analysis. The third section presents the landscape analysis of ontologies relevant to preclinical imaging. The fourth section synthesizes the findings into concrete recommendations on a set of imaging ontologies. These recommendations aim to support harmonisation efforts and enable interoperable standards adoption across imaging communities.

2. Landscape analysis of ontologies relevant to biological imaging

The different potential uses of ontologies means that different aspects of the ontology are of primary interest. Two of the principal ways in which they can be used are:

1. As controlled vocabulary of terms used in metadata values.
2. As a means of providing semantics to the structure of dataset repositories metadata.

In both cases they promote interoperability of data between imaging repositories, reducing or simplifying the work needed to consume data from multiple repositories, but place different requirements on what the ontology needs to cover in order to be useful.

In the former case, where they are used as a controlled vocabulary, class coverage of the subject domain is normally the primary concern. Therefore the classes should clearly denote some unique concept in the ontology subject domain, and collectively should address all relevant concepts. The

connection between these classes, the semantics of which are defined by the properties of the ontology, can also be useful for inference of additional information than that which is stored in the repositories that refer to these terms. In this case they are used as knowledge graphs that describe their subject domain, and it is the statements in the graphs that are of use, rather than just the terms.

In the later case, when used for metadata structure of APIs, property definitions are the primary concern when selecting an ontology to use, as they will be used to provide definitions of the metadata fields. To ensure interoperable data, two fields describing the same semantics should refer to the same property, but a different property should there be any differences in their intended use. The intended goal of this kind of ontology use is often machine-interpretable data, and so the choice of when to use which properties can often be approximated by whether code would be expected to behave differently when handling data using the same ontology terms. Classes in this context are used to provide structure to the property definitions, either in terms of human navigation of the ontology, or through providing rules for expected usage of terms, such as through class disjointness to define clear boundaries between concepts. This use case has similarities with data schemas, as well as more abstract data modelling frameworks or recommendations.

Due to these different intentions in ontology design the landscape analysis and subsequent evaluation of the ontologies will be divided to focus on the specific areas of interest for their intended use.

2.1. Identification of ontologies relevant to biological imaging

Relevant domains

In the bioimaging domain there are multiple subject matters that can benefit from ontology, persistent identifier (PID), or controlled vocabulary use. The majority of the relevant metadata in imaging repositories covers:

- a) general, imaging independent metadata** such as data licencing and authorship, projects, and their funding,
- b) image subject**, such as the species or kinds of cells captured in the field of view, and related information (such as how cells were cultured) if relevant
- c) imaging technique**, such as what was used to produce the signal (electrons or photons), what dyes were used, and what instrument and settings were used,
- d) data processing techniques**, which may be relevant to correlation between images or annotation of image data.

Ontologies for use as a controlled vocabulary of terms

The analysis on ontologies for use as a controlled vocabulary of terms focuses on image subject (b), imaging technique (c), and data processing techniques (d). Ontologies were chosen from the list of those currently in use by the Systems Science of Biological Dynamics Database (SSBD), Image Data Resource (IDR), and BioImage Archive (BIA) imaging database, as well as from searches on biological ontology aggregation services, such as the Ontology Lookup Service (OLS) and BioPortal.

In addition, some non-ontology services were included for context: PID databases can serve a similar purpose in providing unambiguous and unique identifiers that are shared between databases. These are more relevant in identifying people and organizations related to the (a), but also can be used in the identification of samples and protocols.

Ontologies for linked data APIs for imaging datasets

Ontologies for use in linked data APIs must span across domains as data linking, for instance, the image to its subject and imaging techniques will require definitions that the individual domains may not expect to cater for. Ontologies were chosen from Recommended Metadata for Biological Images' (REMBI) list of referenced ontologies and standards, as well as commonly used ontologies that are used for web documents and linked data graphs. In addition, some non-ontology data schemas were included for comparison.

2.2. Evaluation framework for ontologies relevant to biological imaging

Risks and deal-breakers

There can be risks associated with adopting specific ontologies that are not related to their actual content. If these cannot be mitigated, they might be 'deal-breakers' in terms of recommending their adoption, regardless of their content.

- **Licencing concerns:** if use of an ontology is restricted by its licence, or it imposes restrictions on data licensing for data in the repository, then it may not be suitable use.
- **Lack of ongoing maintenance:** if the ontology is no longer maintained, then adopting it may cause eventual issues if it is lacking in domain coverage, or if it is incorrect. This is more of an issue if the subject domain changes rapidly, since it will become out of date sooner.
- **Lack of a Resource Description Framework (RDF) consumable version:** if the intent is to move beyond PID/controlled vocabulary use, and to use the ontology as a knowledge graph to further connect information, then not having an RDF version of the information will make integrating that data into other ontologies much more difficult.

General analysis

For named vocabularies use cases, the number of classes (or some equivalent) in the ontology was noted, both the total number in the ontology, and a note of those only defined by that namespace. The total number of statements is included to give an impression of the quantity of information and 'connectedness' of the ontology. This number could be greatly modified through the materialization of inference rules, so should only be used as an order magnitude impression for their use as knowledge graphs. Finally, the other ontologies that are imported by an ontology are included, as this provides a strong indication of which other ontologies they are designed to work with.

For the linked data API case, terms that correspond to REMBI fields were identified in ontologies of interest, and their total count noted.

2.3. Results of landscape analysis

Overview of ontology statistics

The full landscape analysis is available in tabular form at: [📄 Ontology landscape review - 202506](#). This comprises multiple components of the landscape in particular:

Overview table of currently used schemas/ontologies

This tab provides a high-level overview of 26 distinct ontologies, schemas, and other data-structure related documents, that have potential use in biological image data management. It includes basic information such as ontology names, links, descriptions, classifications, and notes. These 'ontologies' are classified by their typical use. This tab serves as a general reference for the range of ontologies available in the field.

Named Vocabularies - scientific

This more detailed tab contains information on 28 scientific ontologies with a focus on their technical specifications. It includes fields such as acronyms, domains, resource types, repository usage counts, and detailed technical metrics (number of classes, axioms, etc.). The tab has a particular focus on dependencies between ontologies, with the sample entry (Uberon) showing extensive connections to other ontologies like CARO, CHEBI, and RO. This tab provides deeper technical information about scientific domain ontologies relevant to biological imaging.

Named Vocabularies - other domains

This lists 10 ontologies from non-scientific domains that are nonetheless relevant to biological image data management. It covers ontologies related to contributions (e.g., CRediT), institutions, persons, publications, grants, and funding bodies. The classification of these resources includes non-RDF taxonomies, indicating a broader scope of vocabulary types beyond traditional scientific ontologies.

Linked data schema

This tab focuses specifically on five linked data schemas, including Schema.org, that can be applied to biological data. The domains covered include web documents, annotations of web resources, experiments and experimental assets, and general knowledge. This tab emphasizes the semantic web and linked data approaches to representing biological image data.

EFO - OBI source comparison

This tab provides a detailed comparison between the Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) and the Ontology for Biomedical Investigations (OBI), both of which import significant numbers of terms from other ontologies. It aims to illustrate one of the main differences between typical application

ontologies (like EFO) and typical reference ontology (like OBI), even when they are focused on a similar domain, by providing counts of the source ontology of the classes found in both ontologies.

2.4. Further analysis discussion

Experimental Factor Ontology

Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) is an application ontology for services in EMBL-EBI. As such, it mostly uses imported terms from other reference ontologies that are used by EMBL-EBI teams: only 28% of its classes are defined in the Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) namespace, compared to e.g. 83% of Ontology for Biomedical Investigations (OBI) classes being defined in OBI (see [Ontology landscape review - 202506](#) for more details). It does include over 18000 terms defined in its own namespace which provide structure between these ontologies, as well as cover terms that were missing at some point. In addition, it contains some terms which have been deprecated in their original reference ontologies that still exist in data in EMBL-EBI resources.

As an application ontology, EFO provides a curated view of around 40 ontologies. These cover most terms of interest to describe the subject of an image (1 of the 3 main domains of interest for controlled vocabulary use case). The advantage of using this approach is that the curation of the ontology has resulted in the selection of a single term when more than one ontology would cover it: For instance, EFO merges the hierarchies of the Human phenotype ontology (HP) and Mammalian phenotype ontology (MP). While its breadth of coverage from spanning 40 ontologies provides the majority of required terms, and a highly connected graph if used as a knowledge graph. However, since not all terms are imported, it does not provide the same level of depth as any of the individual ontologies it imports from. Additionally, the terms are removed from their original context, and their new placement will have been influenced by their intended use in EMBL-EBI services. This could lead to some semantic drift, perhaps breaking assumptions other users of the ontology may be relying on.

3. Landscape analysis of ontologies relevant to preclinical imaging

A systematic literature review using online databases such as PubMed and Google Scholar was performed to identify domains associated with the preclinical images. For each domain, a search inside the following resources: BioPortal, Ontology Look-up System, and OBO Foundry was performed for identifying and evaluating multiple ontologies that cover the multidisciplinary domain of biomedical imaging.

3.1. Identification of ontologies relevant to preclinical imaging

Relevant Domains

In the preclinical imaging field any image dataset could be associated with several domains, including the imaging modality, the modelled disease, the animal strain and/or the genetic alteration, the body

location (organ or tissue), the investigated drug, the exploited contrast agent or tracer, in addition to the information regarding the experimental protocol, the image acquisition protocols, the analysis procedure, etc. For this reason, the first step involved the identification of the more relevant domains associated with preclinical imaging. Additionally, we included the domain regarding the access/usage of the image dataset, to provide enough information for the reusability of the images. Overall, we identified 14 domains to cover the multi-disciplines of preclinical imaging datasets:

1. Disease
2. Drugs
3. Anatomy
4. Cell Line
5. Genomic
6. Imaging
7. Experimental Conditions
8. Biological, Biomedical Resource
9. Pathology
10. Phenotype
11. Radiology
12. Analysis Ontology
13. Strain
14. Access / Usage

Identification of ontologies

The identification of the ontologies was performed by performing queries in the following resources: BioPortal, Ontology Look-up System, and OBO Foundry based on the selected domains. A total of 35 ontologies were collected, with at least two different ontologies for each domain represented in Figure 1.

Some of the identified ontologies are related to a specific domain, whereas few of them have already been implemented as multi-domain ontologies, therefore they can be exploited to describe more than one domain (e.g. SNOMED, NCIT or EDAM).

Figure 1. Identified domains and the selected ontologies associated with preclinical imaging.

3.2. Evaluation framework for ontologies relevant to preclinical imaging

For a proper evaluation of each ontology, several information were collected, including file formats, number of terms, type of licence, accessibility to the ontology, the date of the last update, number of citations and species coverage (mouse, human or all organisms). All of this information was considered useful to characterize the usability of each ontology. In particular, the availability of different file formats (OWL, CSV, RDF) provides information on how the ontology can be used, as a controlled vocabulary or with a knowledge graph (RDF) for allowing integration with other ontologies. The number of terms (classes) provides information on the coverage of this ontology. The date of the last update is essential to understand whether the ontology is maintained or no longer maintained. The accessibility, i.e. whether the license is free / under a Creative Commons license that allows its reusability under specific conditions, or not, will also affect the usability. The number of citations (for those ontology for which it was possible to extract this figure from the PubMed database) provide a view on the usability and adoption of this ontology within a specific domain and by the research community. The species coverage is intended to address the question whether the ontology was developed specifically for the preclinical domain (that at large exploits mice or small animals), or for the clinical (human species), or if the ontology is cross-species.

All the collected data regarding the landscape analysis is available at [w Ontology_landscape_analysis_preclinical_imaging.docx](#).

4. Recommendations on a set of imaging ontologies

4.1. Recommendations on a set of imaging ontologies for biological imaging

Adopting ontologies

Prior to covering the details of different ontologies, it is important to note that we highly recommend ontology/named vocabulary adoption (as opposed to unstructured text) regardless of which ontology is chosen, whenever feasible (e.g. associating a chemical compound or categorizing a type of imaging process that was performed). Constraining the space of values to a curated set of identifiers already greatly improves interoperability within a database. If two databases use different sets of identifiers for the same concepts, then mappings need only be created between those sets of identifiers, rather than at a dataset-by-dataset level. For many ontologies, such mappings already exist and are being actively worked on. These may be stored in the ontologies themselves (e.g. pubChem and ChEBI contain links to each other's terms) or developed separately (e.g. the Mammalian and Human phenotype ontologies have mappings in one of the mappings-commons github repositories).

Adopting specific controlled vocabularies

All ontologies are a discrete representation of a subject domain designed for a particular use case, and therefore usually provide some form of partial coverage of domain space. Even in a well scoped domain, such as 'the bones of a human body', where it is possible to enumerate every base element, ontologies will have made choices with higher level abstractions to group these terms (e.g. categorizing by position in body, function, or shape). As such, two ontologies describing the same domain might end up with coverage that could be represented as below.

In this case, there will be some terms that represent the same concepts in both ontologies, while others may be very similar. Then there will be some terms that only exist in one ontology, which might be due to a lack of coverage (e.g. some key concept is simply missing) or due to a different approach in representing the domain (e.g. a different categorization system).

Since the majority of use cases for ontologies is as controlled vocabulary rather than as the graph of statements using those terms, it is a reasonable approach to simply use both ontologies and therefore have a large vocabulary to describe the space. When there is overlap, agreeing on a single

ID per concept is all that is needed for data interoperability. Ontologies such as EFO, where terms from multiple ontologies are imported and organised together, have already made these decisions, and often provide mappings between equivalent terms in different ontologies.

Often, two ontologies that are being compared actually aim to capture different domain scope. For instance, the scope of the Mammalian Phenotype Ontology and Human Phenotype Ontology could be represented as follows:

Whereby the two ontologies overlap in subject domain, and have some terms that are equivalent, but have a different distribution of terms in general. In this case favouring the more general ontology should lead to improved interoperability since it will be usable across multiple domains. If a term only exists in the more specific ontology, and mappings of equivalent terms exist, then there is almost no impact to interoperability in using the more specific terms.

Context of these recommendations

A set of ontologies is necessary to cover the various aspects of biological imaging metadata. However, making recommendations is complicated by the fact that ontologies will not necessarily attempt to cover equivalent aspects of this full domain, some ontologies will depend on others, and it is not unreasonable to use terms from multiple ontologies within the same domain for additional coverage. This means that recommendations cannot necessarily be made in isolation of one another.

The recommendations made here are for generic imaging databases that may span multiple domains. If a database is focused on a very specific kind or subject matter for imaging, then it is likely that they should use the most specific ontologies that model those domains. However, it is worth noting that in these cases there is still a tradeoff between specificity and re-use. Unless appropriate mapping exists, or the possibility of traversing a knowledge graph between terms of interest, the more specific terms may not be connected to more general terms used in other databases.

In general, it is taken that ontologies that have a greater number of classes provided more coverage or granularity in a specific domain when being used as named vocabularies, and ontology with a

greater number of properties provide more coverage or granularity when used as terms for a linked data schema.

Ontologies for use as a controlled vocabulary of terms

Recommendations for imaging databases

The ontologies and controlled vocabularies currently used by image archives and ways to harmonise them is discussed in the related deliverable, [D6.1 report](#) (Report in metadata model overlap and gaps). For generalist databases, we recommend using table 2 from this report as a starting point for choosing which ontologies to use to capture metadata. If the database is specific in a certain aspect (e.g. focuses on human samples), using the most appropriate ontology for that aspect (e.g. the human phenotype ontology, rather than mammalian). If some subject domain is not captured in the list above, we recommend looking at the ontologies in use in EFO.

Recommendations for imaging facilities, data stewards, and biologists capturing imaging data.

Capture ontology IDs rather than (or as well as) text description or names. Many ontologies will have guidelines about how to reference their terms: e.g. NCBI taxon recommends NCBI:txid9606 for Homo Sapiens, and OBO ontologies recommend e.g. UBERON:0000948 when it is possible to provide context for the UBERON prefix. Preferably use ontologies that correspond to those in use of any database that may eventually store the data, but do not make that a limiting factor. It is preferable to have some IDs of a different ontology than none at all. If ontologies are missing terms, contact their maintainers to get them added.

Image Subject

This report suggests use of different ontologies and mapping between them where possible, noting this would require establishing a mapping mechanism while leveraging existing ontology mapping tools. The D6.1 report also points out various challenges of this method, including the need for expansion of mapping tools and maintenance and regular updates to the ontologies used.

Imaging technique

We recommend use of either the Biological Imaging Methods Ontology (FBbi) or EDAM ontologies. For newer resources, we would suggest EDAM due to its active maintenance status, however we are developing mapping tools between the ontologies to support the use of either.

Ontologies for linked data APIs for imaging datasets

On ontologies for use in repository metadata data structure (i.e. their use to turn data schemas into linked-data schema). There are a number of generic data management ontologies which are appropriate for capturing the majority of non-image specific data. For instance schema.org provides suitable properties for describing authorship, affiliation, and aspects of documents, such as title, descriptions, and keywords. Dublin core can also be used for generic identifier keys.

There are also a number of ontologies that aim to capture scientific processes, protocols, assays etc. such as Just Enough Results Model ontology (JERM), and OBI, and even BFO. These cover many of the

classes that would be necessary to model the typical metadata associated with biological images, but none really cover descriptions of, for instance, the fields described in REMBI, to a level that the different fields would be clearly distinguishable with different properties in an ontology.

Existing data model schemas for imaging repositories do not seem to have dedicated RDF based ontology terms to describe their fields, nor do the high-level recommendations such as REMBI. As such, there may be a need for any repositories that want to provide a linked-data representation of their data to define such an ontology. In this case, parenting new classes to classes in JERM, OBI, EDAM, and BFO are likely to be the best candidates.

4.2. Recommendations on a set of imaging ontologies for preclinical imaging

The processes for scoring, selecting, and recommending the preclinical ontologies are documented in Deliverable 4.1 [W D4_1_Report on the recommended ontologies for preclinical image datasets.d...](#). We refer the reader to D4.1 for comprehensive details on these activities.